

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND RISKS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the transition to digital economy, such as experiences, achievements, and risks, in which we can have visions of the extent to which the transition to digitization gives advances for each state or region and what awaits us through digitization in the future. Facts about the impact of the development of the digital economy on people, business and the state have been cited.

Keywords: Economy, globalization, internet, digital economy, expectations, new markets, time and people, risks.

INTRODUCTION

In general, the most active driver of the digital economy is the state. He is the main customer and consumer of the digital economy. For example, China spent around \$ 9bn for these purposes. The Alibaba internet resource, which has a market capitalization of more than \$ 210 billion, has proven that these investments are focused correctly.

The state, which wants to get the maximum benefit from digitization, needs to create and support the market for the necessary high-tech products. At the same time, it is also important to maintain the instruments controlling the main platforms of the electronic economy in its own izm, developing in a parallel way private applications for Public Administration, important industries and enterprises.

In particular, Japan, despite its procurement of technologies, missed leading positions in the digital economy due to the inability to create its own producer networks in this direction and keep the level of technical developments in a consistently high state. South Korea, on the other hand, is investing in e-government and e-mediation (for e-commerce activities and public tender purchases) in amounts equivalent to 1% of the national budget, generating \$ 10-15 billion each year and generating income that covers expenses 30-40 times. In particular, such a result was achieved by organizing call centers in the public and private sector, creating mobile applications and reinvigorating state-owned internet platforms.

The economic importance of the digital sector

It is noted that digital technologies dramatically change more than 50 percent of economy-related industries. This vision is based on the fact that information technology and digital platforms dramatically change business models, eliminating intermediaries and optimizing processes in their effectiveness. According to World Bank estimates, it turns out that a 10 percent increase in fast internet users can increase the annual GDP from 0.4 percent to 1.4 percent. Also, the growth of the share of the digital economy in the country's GDP by about 20 percent each year (in developed countries, this figure is around 7 percent) is considered as an indicator that determines its importance. In 2010, Boston Consulting Group estimated the scale of digitization at \$ 2.3-16 trillion (4.1 percent GDP) for a group of 20 countries. If this trend is maintained, then after 10-15 years the share of

such an economy in world GDP will approach 30-40 percent. In developing economies, about 1 percent of the population works in the IT sector, this sector creates jobs relatively whip compared to others. However, the rise of the IT direction gives impetus to the creation of jobs in other areas that are mastering new technologies (for every 1 new jobs created in the IT sector, there are 4.9 jobs in related areas). The 5-digit economy boldly reveals new horizons to entrepreneurs and people who work for themselves. Often, the contribution to the development of the IT sector sets the stage for the development of the economy, the creation of new jobs, the emergence of new types of services for people and business, and the reduction in their costs within the framework of e-government projects. At the same time, the overall effect generated from the implementation of information technology turns out to be more inefficient than expected and is not distributed in the same order. To get the maximum result from this type of investment, it is necessary to have a good understanding of the interaction of technologies with other factors, called "analog fillers", in a report prepared by the World Bank.

Among them:

- a regulatory framework that supports an active business environment and allows businesses and people to use digital economy technologies for competition and innovation, cost-cutting, as well as for improving living well-being;
- full-fledged skills in the application of Information Technology in business management and civil servants;
- in the direction of the use of Information Technology are institutions (public and private) that provide consulting services.

The full enumeration of the effects generated by the digital economy is a much more complex work, consequently, the possibility of using electronic services and metadata is much more difficult to assess in a full-fledged way the connections that it offers to economic objects. Therefore, it is a somewhat difficult task to justify the importance of investments in informatization, especially at the state level. The impossibility of always calculating the gigabyte of information created in one area or another in the real state is an understandable phenomenon in itself.

Communication models resulting from the integration of information platforms give impetus to the emergence of new economic technologies (YaITs). YaIT is the sum of new "configurable" tools and

methods in every respect related to the processing of information (information, ideas and knowledge) products that serve organizational management systems for some purpose, combining them into a holistic technological platform for transmission, storage and reflection, and maximizing the cost of transaction spent on communication of economic agents.

Basic principles of YaIT:

- creating fundamentally new business models.
- application of methods of rational integration and use of various IT services in organizational and technological processes in the real economy sector;
- transactional costs and material used in production minimizing resources.

Growth guarantees in digital sales

YaIT is developing in existing economic realities based on digital technologies. While earlier technologies related to production, trade and finance improved in stages, the now-emerging Yaits serve as a backbone to horizontal relations (self-organization and singularity), innovative entrepreneurship (self-development), Information Engineering (self-improvement) and autoformalization of economic processes (automatic structure).

The true basis of yaIT is formed by data centers and modern IT platforms designed for systematization and analytical processing of information. It is important to develop the direction of providing services related to management consulting and business analysis. New institutions, such as information and consulting services and state development agencies, serve as the organizational basis for improving the business environment.

Development of the digital economy

Digital age, digital economy, digital social life. How quickly these words have entered our lives, from which we begin to benefit, we all understand well that we are working as a branch of this system. Due to the fact that the digital economy covers the whole world, any public project on informatization and digitization should be studied in complex and on the basis of identification of information related to a single coding system, economic and management.

The most important aspect and at the same time the most complex stage in the development of the digital economy is the simplification of the business environment and the maximum reduction in the costs that will be spent on the communication of people and business with the state.

After that, the parties are inter-organizational within the public and private sector

(multiagent) communication is required.

Digital economy platforms, which go from the "one-to-one" and "one-to-many" communication formula to the "multiple" formula, are the most important branch of this process. Shifts in this area, through the development of consulting and technical organizations suitable for small and medium-sized businesses with the support of the state, will automatically dramatically change the situation in the real sector of the economy (and give

impetus to structural reforms in these areas) and help create conditions for an innovative economy.

Risks of digital social life

In all the industrial revolutions up to this time, the society was concerned about unemployment. However, these concerns did not justify themselves—each industrial revolution served to reduce the unemployment rate. New occupations created after 1990 alone account for 8% of total occupations. With the creation of the internet, the number of new professions increased dramatically. With the spread of new technologies, the new industrial revolution also creates professions that did not exist before. In this way, it can be hoped that the unemployment rate will not increase in the following years. For example, in the 19th century, when 90% of the total population worked in agriculture, now this figure does not exceed 2%. Similarly, the "mobile application economy" () generated more than \$ 150bn in revenue in 2018, and this figure is increasing every year. Given that this sector did not exist at all until just 10 years ago, trends in the current economy change are more evident. Even if humanity is able to overcome such problems as income inequality and job losses, the use of digital technologies in every possible way creates other problems. In particular, the biggest problem is the loss of personality of personal information. The fact that all information about you is available on the general network also causes many big problems. It is in some way better for the AI mentioned by some experts to anticipate information about you, and when we take it from the other side, it also causes great problems behind itself. For example, you posted a picture of what you liked on a social network, because of the fact that your financial situation is not enough to get it right now, you are pushing the purchase back. Artificial intelligence with all the information about you, on the other hand, will immediately find information about it and offer you a special personalized bank loan. No matter how much experts talk about this technology making your daily routine easier, it's not that good that others influence your decision-making process. Continuing with the above idea, the concept of advertising, which is personified in the hoirgi day, has become a normal situation on the internet. Artificial intelligence will be what you need, taking into account your interests, thoughts offers things. With the advent of the Internet of things, advertising on the internet now covers all banners and other advertising media. This in turn causes people to over-consume what they need, to enter into more bank debts. A recent study has shown that, as of the present day, artificial intelligence knows people much better and that the WAG offers what it needs. For example, clicking on the "like" ending on an overseas picture of an acquaintance on a social network means that for AI you also have an interest in traveling, and it will begin to offer you tours for a special trip. Various internet sites, gadgets offer advertising on this, recording not only your history of likes, but also your daily conversation. If, simply, you ask a friend where Toys for dogs are sold immediately your phone will also

hear this conversation and start advertising you the nearest results on the search for “toys for dogs”. While many believe that it is accessible to everyone, that it is possible to find the necessary things more easily, any thought that affects the decision-making process of people can cause great harm. Therefore, the new industrial revolution seriously affects our decision-making, changing the daily lives of each of us. Another problem that is born in a new time is also the data goes back to confidentiality. That is, in later times, such concepts as cyberattacks, “phishing”, “spamming”, “fraud” increased. While you are previously sure that your own money is hollow in your pocket, it is now difficult to keep it so reliable through various hacking attacks in the time of electronic money. The increase in money in electronic form in its place leads to an increase in this type of problem. On the other hand, the sale of personal information by large companies to the Security Services Authority and advertising agencies also causes significant problems. Determinism (the principle of cause and effect) is always controversial. But it can be said For sure-that no one can stop the development. This is a process that is in constant progress (growth).

2 Conclusions

We hope you find the information in this template useful in the preparation of your submission.

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